

Prioritizing climate smart agriculture interventions to support policy-making

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What is CSA...

... is agriculture that sustainably...

Productivity

increases the **productivity** and agricultural incomes

Adaptation

enhances resilience (Climate change **Adaptation**)

Mitigation

reduces/removes GHG emissions where possible (**Mitigation**)

CSA pillars

CSA synergies and trade-offs

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Source: adapted from Vermeulen et al. (2012)

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CPH Tools & methodologies across the decision-making process

- CSA Profiles
- Sub-National Profiles
- CRVA

- CBA Tool
- MACC

- AMIA Villages
- CSV Guidelines

- Foresight modelling
- CSVC
- CSA investment plans

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CSA Practices Smartness Assessment

CSA Practices

Rice

- Alternate Wetting and Drying
- Solar powered irrigation
- Buried pipe irrigation
- Salt/submergence/drought tolerant HYV
- Urea deep placement

Non-rice crops

- Heat and salinity tolerant HYV (wheat)
- Increasing shares of non-rice crops in rabi season (replacing boro)
- Reduction of soil acidity (liming)

Livestock

- Improved feed for indigenous and improved cattle
- Adoption of improved breeds
- Biogas for cattle and poultry manure management

Fisheries

- Increase pond area with cultivation of small indigenous fish species
- Conversion of extensive to semi-intensive fishponds
- Increase of floodplain cultivation yields

Results examples: trends with and w/o CSA packages

GHG emissions in MtCO₂

Mitigation

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Water use in million liters

Adaptation

Profits in MIO taka

Self-sufficiency (% kcal)

Productivity

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Conclusion

- Climate Smart Agriculture is highly context specific → no one size fit all solution
- Key to have a structured process for CSA planning
- For CSA planning it is important to
 - Understand the context and challenges of the agriculture sector at various scales
 - Evaluation financial implications for farmers and economic return for society
 - Piloting might be necessary, especially for new technologies and practices
 - Important to also keep in mind the bigger picture and how CSA interventions will related to long-term policy objectives
- Once we know what to do, innovative financial services and support need to be put into place as well as targeted incentives (fiscal reform, climate smart subsidies, etc)

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CSA Prioritization Framework

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Source: adapted from Campbell *et al.* (2016), Andrieu *et al.* (2017)

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